

Portable and low cost photoluminescence(PL) spectrometer for micro- and nanoplastics detection - Initial DMP

I. Data summary

Provide a summary of the data addressing the following issues:

- State the purpose of the data collection/generation
- Explain the relation to the objectives of the project
- Specify the types and formats of data generated/collected
- Specify if existing data is being re-used (if any)
- Specify the origin of the data
- State the expected size of the data (if known)
- Outline the data utility: to whom will it be useful

Data collection and generation will enable me to answer relevant questions, evaluate outcomes and make predictions about future probabilities and trends. Accurate data collection is essential to maintaining the integrity of research, making informed decisions, and ensuring quality assurance. It will also help me in opening the way for international and multi/interdisciplinary training, career development, and research collaborations among other researchers.

Relation to the project's objectives:

- Enhance our capability to detect, trace the origin, determine the toxicity, and ultimately separate micro and nano plastics from myriad environmental matrices.
- It will help in standardizing the methods for micro and nano plastics detection

The data type will be generated in different formats i.e.

Type	Volume	Storage/Dissemination	Expiration	Format
Review Article	MB	Personal Hard drive	N/A	.docx .pdf .jpg
Images (of samples, devices, ...)	MB	Personal Hard drive Personal BOX space	N/A (To be preserved)	.jpeg .png
Raw PL and absorption spectroscopy spectral data	GB	Personal Hard drive Personal BOX space Research Group BOX space	N/A (To be preserved)	.wdf .spc
Processed spectral data	GB	Personal Hard Drive Instrument PC Research Group BOX space	N/A (To be preserved)	.wdf .spc

Modeling and Simulation files using COMSOL	GB	Personal Hard drive Personal BOX space Research Group BOX space	N/A (To be preserved)	.mph
PhD progress reports	MB	Aston University AiPT repository MONPLAS Box platform Research Group BOX space	N/A	.docx .txt .pdf
PhD progress presentations	MB	Aston University AiPT repository Research Group BOX space MONPLAS Box platform	N/A	.pptx
Research Publications (Journal and Conferences)	MB	Personal Hard Drive Research Group BOX space Journals repository DOAJ ZENODO LinkedIn	N/A (To be preserved)	.docx .txt .pdf
Programing files	GB	Personal Hard drive Instrument PC GitHub ZENODO	N/A (To be preserved)	python
MONPLAS Project Dissemination and Outreach Data	MB	Personal Hard Drive MONPLAS Box platform	3 years (To be preserved)	.mp3 .mp4 .wav

Origin of data:

Aston University: Data origin is from analytical instruments: Absorption and photoluminescence spectrometers.

Size: 6TB, major part of the data will be from simulation (COMSOL)

To whom will it be useful?

The data acquired will be shared with the MONPLAS consortium and other interested

parties and also will be useful for the researchers who will further work on PL for the detection of MPs.

2. FAIR data

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for

- **metadata: Outline the discoverability of data**
(metadata provision)
- **Outline the identifiability of data and refer to standard identification mechanism. Do you make use of persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers?**
- **Outline naming conventions used**
- **Outline the approach towards search**
- **keywordOutline the approach for clear versioning**
- **Specify standards for metadata creation (if any). If there are no standards in your discipline describe what metadata will be created and how**

All the research data produced during my research at Aston University will be stored in the [Aston Research Data Explorer](#) preferably with a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) and will be made identifiable, accessible and discoverable, and reusable. Lab notebooks, diaries, copies will be created as a backup.

Keywords related to research data sets will be associated to the data in the Aston Research Data Explorer. Spectroscopy standards ontologies and vocabularies will be priority for the next versions, following further research, as MONPLAS is currently engaging the community for the most operational examples available.

- Uploaded metadata will contain the following details: data description, authors, institutes, funding bodies and date and time data creation.
- Open metadata is a priority to be resolved for the next version following community standards where they exist.
- Metadata uploaded on Aston server with specified formats will comprise of all information including author, funding source, data description and date of creation.

2.2 Making data openly accessible:

- **Specify which data will be made openly available? If some data is kept closed provide rationale for doing so**
- **Specify how the data will be made available**
- **Specify what methods or software tools are needed to access the data? Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included? Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?**
- **Specify where the data and associated metadata, documentation and code are deposited**
- **Specify how access will be provided in case there are any restrictions**

Openly accessible:

We at Aston, are taking steps to ensure open access data as required by the Horizon 2020 program. All data and metadata will be stored in commonly used formats that do not require specially designed software or tools to read/write them. Initial manuscripts (pre-prints) and the final versions with peer reviewed and corrections (post-prints) will be made freely available following their publications in preprints and Green Open Access repositories. At Aston University, we will be following The 'green' route to open access as: the copies of the peer-reviewed research articles of the MONPLAS project will be made freely available as soon as possible once published.

How the metadata will be made available?

Metadata of our research will be stored in the Aston Publications Explorer and will be openly available online once put in the repository and unless restricted by publisher or partner companies where I will perform experiments. METADATA will be freely accessible at the deposit as requested by EC funding contract, however data access may be delayed in synergy with MONPLAS Exploitation Management Committee requirements on Commercialization and Industry Partner.

Methods or tools required for accessing data:

At the moment there are no specific software tools required to access the data produced in my project. But at Aston, data stored in Aston Data Explorer will be accessible and be freely used.

Where data and associated metadata are deposited?

All the data including images, spectral data, simulation files, programming data, peer-reviewed journal and conference research articles (including research posters in conferences) will be deposited (restricted if necessary) in our Aston Data Explorer.

How access will be provided in case there are any restrictions?

Aston University provides open access to the data. There are two categories of Open access here at Aston which is Green and Gold.

Green Open Access: The Green route is our default way of ensuring compliance with OA requirements and makes the full text freely available on Aston's research repository ([Aston Publications Explorer](#)) at the end of a publisher embargo period (typically between 6 and 24 months).

Gold Open Access: Gold Open Access requires payment of an Article Processing Charge (APC) and makes the final published PDF open access immediately from the publisher's website; Gold OA charges may be covered by a transformative agreement with a publisher or by a one-off payment. Authors will be supported in making their publications OA by Library Services

Aston Research Explorer

Aston Research Explorer is where you can discover information about our staff, research units, research outputs, awards and activities. To access our publication repository click on [Aston Publications Explorer](#), and to access our data repository, go to [Aston Data Explorer](#). Do you have a profile and want to make changes or want to add research

2.3 Making data interoperable:

- **Assess the interoperability of your data. Specify what data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies you will follow to facilitate interoperability.**
- **Specify whether you will be using standard vocabulary for all data types present in your data set, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability? If not, will you provide mapping to more commonly used ontologies?**

What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, or methodologies you will follow to facilitate interoperability?

Our research data and metadata will be given keywords (Spectroscopy standard ontologies and vocabularies will be priority to be resolved for the next version following further research) as open metadata is a priority to be resolved for the next version following the community standards where they exist, easily findable names with dates, and proper experiment names which will indicate and direct the finder to access its smoothly. Other ways to make it more interoperable are to follow non-proprietary/open-source formats where possible like issue and version numbers. Moreover, interoperability can be facilitated by using collection methods, date of creation, license type, author names, funding bodies, and organizations.

Yes, we will be using standard vocabulary for all data types produced in our research.

2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses):

- **Specify how the data will be licensed to permit the widest reuse possible**
- **Specify when the data will be made available for re-use. If applicable, specify why and for what period a data embargo is needed**
- **Specify whether the data produced and/or used in the project is useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use**

- **of some data is restricted, explain why**
- **Describe data quality assurance processes**
- **Specify the length of time for which the data will remain re-usable**

How the data will be licensed to permit the widest reuse possible?

The Creative Common License will be associated at the time when the data will be deposited in the repository.

When the data will be made available for re-use. If applicable, specify why and for what period a data embargo is needed?

Our research data will be made available immediately for re-use upon deposition in the repository unless embargoed by the publisher or restricted by the MONPLAS Exploitation Management Committee. We aim to implement entire FAIR and Open Data in synergy with commercialization needs and considerations by the MONPLAS Exploitation Management Committee and industrial policies. Metadata will be openly accessible on online platforms at publication date.

Specify whether the data produced and/or used in the project is useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why?

Currently, at Aston, we are providing open access to the data which will be produced in MONPLAS project through our online platform (Aston Data Explorer). But at later stages, we are not sure if the re-use of the data will be restricted, we will provide valid reasons for that which would be either publisher or consortium partners. We aim to provide entire open access to our research data intelligently in consultation with MONPLAS EMC and basic principles of IPR outlined by the Eruption Commission IPR.

Length of time for which data will remain re-usable:

At Aston University the MONPLAS data will be stored and available for re-use in AstonData Explorer for a minimum of 10 years. With the permission of Aston Data Explorer team all the data will be stored in ZENODO.

3. Allocation of resources

Explain the allocation of resources, addressing the following issues:

- **Estimate the costs for making your data FAIR. Describe how you intend to cover these costs**
- **Clearly identify responsibilities for data management in your project**
- **Describe costs and potential value of long term preservation**

Estimate the costs for making your data FAIR. Describe how you intend to cover these costs?

Our long-term produced research data will be stored in Aston Data Explorer and will be carried out by the Aston University. Regarding the cost of which is covered by Aston University.

Clearly identify responsibilities for data management in your project?

For my project, my primary and secondary supervisors are responsible for data management but for the MONPLAS, the Project Coordinator (who is also my secondary supervisor) with the input from the project management team is responsible for data management.

Describe costs and potential value of long term preservation:

At Aston, for a minimum period of 10 years (long-term preservation), the data will be stored and the cost will be covered by the university.

4. Data security

Address data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data

In my project, addressing data recovery, storage, and transfer of sensitive data will be proceeded by following ways:

- The security of the data will be ensured by keeping it in the local computer, laptop, and portable drives as well as on online forums (Google drive and box.com).
- I will ensure that the data are preserved securely and in full compliance with European Union data protection laws.
- Output research data stored in Aston Data Explorer is archived through Arkivum. Arkivum has an ISO 27001 data security certification

5. Ethical aspects

To be covered in the context of the ethics review, ethics section of DoA and ethics deliverables. Include references and related technical aspects if not covered by the former

Good research ethics will be ensured to take great care and avert any case where sensitive information could get misused.

I will ensure to process personal data under the GA in accordance with EU and national law on

data protection (in particular, Directive 95/46/EC and the corresponding national law).

- Ethical principles (including the highest standards of research integrity — as set out, for instance, in the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity including, in particular, avoiding fabrication, falsification, plagiarism, or other research misconduct)
- Applicable international, EU, and national law (in particular, EU Directive 95/46/EC).

6. Other

Refer to other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management that you are using (if any)

We have an IT department that ensures the protection and preservation of data and they will provide us better and long-term safe and secure data storage.